

**КЛІНІКО-ІНСТРУМЕНТАЛЬНІ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКИ ПАЦІЄНТІВ З
ПЕРСИСТЕНТНОЮ ФІБРИЛЯЦІЄЮ ПЕРЕДСЕРДЬ З ЗАПЛАНОВАНОЮ
ЕЛЕКТРИЧНОЮ КАРДІОВЕРСІЄЮ,
В ЗАЛЕЖНОСТІ ВІД ТРИВАЛОСТІ ПАРОКСИЗМУ**

**CLINICAL AND INSTRUMENTAL CHARACTERISTICS OF PATIENTS WITH
PERSISTENT ATRIAL FIBRILLATION WITH PLANNED ELECTRICAL
CARDIOVERSION, DEPENDING ON THE DURATION OF PAROXISM**

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The aim of the work is to compare the clinical, instrumental and laboratory characteristics of patients with persistent atrial fibrillation (PeAF) depending on the duration of paroxysm of atrial fibrillation (AF)

Materials and methods: in a single-center retrospective study we have analyzed data obtained from a clinical and instrumental examination of 118 patients with PeAF with a duration of paroxysm from 7 days, who underwent sinus rhythm restoration procedure by electrical cardioversion (ECV). Depending on the duration of the paroxysm of PeAF, all patients were divided into two: I - group with PeAF episode < 90 days (n = 58) II group with PeAF ≥90 days (n = 60).

Results: in the compared groups there were statistically significant differences in the reduction of the left ventricular systolic function (LV EF <40%): 2 (3.5%) patients of the I group against 12 (20.3%) patients of II group, p=0,014. Also, according to transesophageal echocardiography (TEE), there was a difference in the left atrial appendage (LAA) flow velocity: 43.5 cm/sec vs. 37.0 cm/sec, p=0.020. Differences in left atrial volume index (LAVI) did not reached statistical significance (98 (80-110) vs. 99 (86-114) ml/m², p=0.088). In both compared groups we have registered a large proportion of patients with reduction of glomerular filtration rate (GFR): mild reduction of GFR (60-89 ml/min/1.73 m²) in 36 (62.1%) patients of the I group and 38 (63.3%) patients of the II group, and moderate reduction of GFR (<60 ml/min/1.73 m²) in 12 (27.6%) patients of the I group and 18 (30.0%) patients of the II group.

Conclusions: According to our results both groups are statistically homogenous in the most clinical, instrumental and laboratory parameters. The duration of an episode of AF ≥ 90 days is associated with more frequent left ventricle systolic dysfunction and reduction of the LAA function.

Key words: persistent atrial fibrillation, electrical cardioversion, heart failure.